

**Consumer Emotional Attachment
towards Brand of Personal Care
Products**

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the concept of consumer emotional attachment to personal care brands, seeking to understand the key factors that affect consumers' emotional bonds with these products. In a competitive marketplace where product features are frequently similar, emotional attachment is crucial for driving brand loyalty and influencing purchasing decisions. Utilizing a quantitative research techniques, such as detailed surveys, this study investigates the emotional aspects of consumers' connections with personal care brands. The research sample includes individuals from various demographic backgrounds, enabling a thorough examination of emotional attachment across different consumer groups.

Keywords: Consumer, Brand Loyalty, Emotional attachment and Personal Care Product

INTRODUCTION

Emotional branding is critical in marketing as customer emotional attachment towards a brand such as feelings of sympathy, sadness, pride, and anger results in distinct meaning of the individual's environment and therefore has unique motivational implications towards the choice and decision making.

According to Thomson, McInnis & Park (2005), emotional Attachment to Brands, studies focusing on the nature and character of brand attachment approach this complex domain from somewhat different viewpoints. Marketers use tactics such as a young

child or an animal to capture the hearts of the audience. This bond between the customer and the brand affects the behaviour of the customer, which in turn can foster the firm's profitability and the customer's value to the firm. It is a basic human need to want to form an attachment. Customers can form emotional attachments to an array of objects such as collectibles, gifts and of course brands.

Despite the fact that an emotional attachment to an object is unlikely to be similar in strength as an attachment between two humans, the fundamental properties and behavioural effects of emotional attachment are similar. Emotional attachment to a brand is underpinned by love, affection and connection towards the brand. These components of emotional attachment convey that a customer with a stronger emotional attachment is likely to be more committed and emotionally attached to a brand.

Emotional attachment at a higher level is likely to increase a customer's emotional need for the brand. As the customer becomes more united with a brand, they are likely to stay relatively close with the brand as the presence of the brand offers feelings of enjoyment, delight, and security.

This concludes that a customer with higher levels of attachment to a brand is more likely to commit to being in a long-term relationship with the brand. Marketers need to ensure they are reaching the right kind of emotions within the consumer, which correlate with the brand.

➤ **Brand:**

A brand is a product or a business that has a distinct identity in the perception of consumers. The brand is created through elements of design, packaging, and advertising that, as a whole, distinguish the product from its competitors.

A brand is an intangible asset made up of many elements. Together these elements help consumers identify a product and give them reasons to buy it rather than its competitors.

The brand may convey a message that the product is more effective, easier to use, better tasting, cheaper, classier, hipper, or more environmentally sound than its competitors.

History of Brands:

The concept of branding may go as far back as 2000 B.C., when merchants began considering how they could sell their wares more effectively. Merchants in ancient Babylon developed sales pitches to lure in customers. Craftsmen branded or carved symbols on their merchandise to indicate their origin. Tavern owners hung attractive signs outside.

The word "branding" for product marketing might have come into use in the 19th century when Western cattle ranchers started using hot irons to mark their livestock with the ranch's initials or a symbol. Their initial purpose was less marketing than protection from cattle rustlers, but the association stuck.

Branding as mass marketing took off in the 19th century, as sellers of products like flour began thinking about ways to distinguish themselves from their competitors.

Types of Brands:

The type of brand used depends on the entity using it. The following are some of the most common forms of brands:

- **Corporate Brands:** Corporate branding is a way for companies to enhance their reputations and distinguish themselves from competitors in their industries. The company's pricing, mission, target market, and values all reflect the corporate brand.
- **Personal Brands:** Social media enabled ordinary people to become influencers. Their financial success depends on their ability to create a brand that attracts an audience that certain advertisers want to reach. Personal brands are built through social media posts, sharing images and videos, and conducting meet-and-greets.
- **Product Brands:** Introducing a new product or supporting an existing product involves creating and maintaining its brand. Branding a product starts with market research and identifying the right target market.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK:

Customer-based brand equity (CBBE) is used to show how a brand's success can be directly attributed to customers' attitudes towards that brand.

The 4 levels of Keller's CBBE model

Level 1: Brand identity (who are you?)

This is how customers look at your brand and distinguish it from others. It explores the words and images buyers associate with when they hear a particular brand name. It's the most important level and must be strong to support the rest of the pyramid above it. Brand identity quantifies the breadth and depth of customer awareness of a brand. Start to build it when customers are unaware of your products and values, attracting them with ad campaigns and targeted marketing.

Level 2: Brand meaning (what are you?)

Once customers become aware of your brand, they'll want to know more about your product. They'll question its features, looks and style, reliability, durability, customer experience and value for money, to find its brand meaning. For the purposes of brand reputation, Level 2 is split into two categories:

Brand performance: This covers product functionality, reliability, durability, and price as well as customer service and satisfaction. It's 'it does what it says on the tin' territory and when it performs well, customer opinion will be positive.

Brand imagery: different, but equally important, imagery meets the customers' social and psychological needs. What does the brand appear to be to customers? Volvo appears Scandi-chic, family-orientated, safe and eco-responsible; Cushelle soft, homely and cozy. This messaging can come out in targeted marketing and word of mouth.

Level 3: Brand response (what are the feelings for the brand?)

On this level of Keller's model, judgment and feelings can be hard to separate and are intensely personal for each individual customer. One customer may judge the brand irrelevant to them, whereas another will find it completely relevant. Another may make their own value comparison against another product, harshly or fairly. And add to the mix actual interaction and perceived reputation and you can see how hard it can be to quantify how customers feel about a brand and how much they trust it. Companies need to respond to judgments and build positive feelings about the brand once they know what they are.

Level 4: Brand resonance (a strong relationship)

The apex of Keller's CBBE model is resonance: when a customer is loyal to a brand, considers it superior, will buy no other and advocates its merits to others. Many things resonate with customers: lifetime experience, customer service, products and value. A good measure for resonance is the Net Promoter Score that asks one simple question: 'How likely is it that you would recommend [Product X] to a friend or colleague?'

Keller's model is deceptively beautiful in its simplicity; building customer-based brand equity is, in reality, a long and hard road. When you start at the bottom with a great brand identity, then get customers to know your brand and your business gradually, you'll create a brand that people will like, trust and which will ultimately be successful.

LITERATURE REVIEWS

(Rah21, 2021) Emotion is an inseparable characteristic of human and human behaviour and is dominant in human behaviour consciously and unconsciously. Brands and products interact with consumer emotionally and even elicit emotion. This emotion influence consumer behaviour in pre-purchase phase, purchase phase and post-purchase and may be positive or negative.

(Sharma, 2023) Emotions are important in purchase decisions. Rational and emotional aspects together influence choices and decisions, both in social and business events. This paper is about how emotional marketing affects consumer behaviour and how emotions will affect the decision-making process of the consumers. To know the consumers' response to different kinds of emotions, 150 samples were collected randomly using a questionnaire. The questions included how emotions affect them in various situations, which type of emotions they feel often, and how they feel after purchasing a product

(Kaufmann, 2021) Corporate and local managers should always be aware of opportunities to build and to consistently re-build brand identity and communicate a message to consumers that leads present and future customers to feel identification with the brand. Customers need to feel that the brand symbolizes what they are; this contributes to the customer's image and helps to develop a sense of belonging.

(McInnis, 2020) In this research, consumers were asked to self-select a brand, corresponding to varying degrees of emotional attachment as directed by the respective instrument condition that they received. An alternative data collection methodology would be to use a common brand and ask consumers to report their emotional attachment to only that specific brand. One advantage of this methodology is that the brand would be constant across all emotional attachment conditions.

(Rahmanian, 2019) Brands and products live in consumers' minds. Organizations give meanings to them (or at least try to do so) but consumers give identity to brands and products. Brand forms in consumer's mind by brands related experiences and their emotions. We studied emotion from psychology, marketing and product views to gain a better understanding of emotion in consumer behaviour.

(K. Prabhakar Rajkumar, 2019) This study explores the consumer emotional attachment to the brand. A brand that can build up an emotional attachment with consumers plays a significant role in building up an emotional attachment and bonding in the market domain. The research paper used the CHAID, the decision tree method appears in the literature review with different names as automatic interaction detection, classification and regression tree, artificial neural network and genetic algorithm to evaluate the brand experience and attachment level, which create an emotional link with consumers, which are categorized in two groups i.e. Mediocre and Obsession.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

- It allows companies to understand how deeply customers connect with their products.
- It will leads to increase brand loyalty of consumers towards personal care product.
- It will higher the purchase frequency of Personal care product.
- It will ultimately greater profitability by tapping into emotions like self-esteem, confidence, and well-being associated with personal care items; essentially creating a stronger, more meaningful relationship between the consumer and the brand.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- a. To study different factors affecting that contribute to emotional attachment towards a brand.
- b. To assess the influence of satisfaction on brand emotional attachment.
- c. To understand the influence of Price on brand emotional attachment.
- d. To understand the influence of quality on brand emotional attachment.

HYPOTHESIS

H0: (1) There is no significant difference between Quality and Emotional Attachment across gender for personal care product.

H1: (1) There is significant difference between Quality and Emotional Attachment across gender for personal care product.

H0: (2) There is no significant difference between Price and Emotional Attachment across gender for personal care product.

H1: (2) There is significant difference between Price and Emotional Attachment across gender for personal care product.

H0: (3) There is no significant difference between Satisfaction and Emotional Attachment across gender for personal care product.

H1: (3) There is significant difference between Satisfaction and Emotional Attachment across gender for personal care product.

H0: (4) There is no significant difference between Quality and Emotional Attachment across age for personal care product.

H1: (4) There is significant difference between Quality and Emotional Attachment across age for personal care product.

H0: (5) There is no significant difference between Price and Emotional Attachment across age for personal care product.

H1: (5) There is significant difference between Price and Emotional Attachment across age for personal care product.

H0: (6) There is no significant difference between Satisfaction and Emotional Attachment across age for personal care product.

H1: (6) There is significant difference between Satisfaction and Emotional Attachment across age for personal care product.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is descriptive. The study is an attempt to measure the factors affecting consumer emotional attachment towards brands that are quality, price and satisfaction. The study also explores demographic factors, namely age and gender, on the overall consumer emotional attachment towards personal care brands in Bharuch city. Non-Probability sampling was used for this study (Convenience Sampling).

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

Sr No	STATEMENTS	PARAMETER
1	The quality is maintained consistently by the brand	QUALITY
2	The brand offers good quality of products in all variants	
3	Quality is a main factor for my repurchase intention of brand products	
4	Product of the brand lead to gain my trust on the brand	
5	The company takes care of quality during the make of the brand	
6	I am satisfied with the service provided by brand stores	PRICE
7	Brand product is considered to be a good buy	
8	The brand is a perfect fit for my personality	
9	I am satisfied with the support received from brand that resolved my recent problem	SATISFACTION
10	I like commitment of brand to meet my product expectation	
11	I don't look at alternative brands	
12	I would continue to buy the product if its prices increase	
13	Brand products reflect positive about me in eyes of other people	

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Quality_mea	.097	162	<.001	.971	162	.002
Price_mea	.132	162	<.001	.974	162	.003
Satisfaction_mea	.063	162	.200*	.992	162	.524

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

As we can see in table, the significance value is less than 0.05 so we will use Non Parametric test.

STATISTICAL TEST ANALYSIS:

MANN WHITNEY U TEST			
GENDER			
Variable	HO	Value	Interpretation
Quality	Rejected	0.031	Difference
Price	Accepted	0.456	No difference
Satisfaction	Accepted	0.069	No difference
KRUSKAL WALLIS TEST			
AGE			
Variable	HO	Value	Interpretation
Quality	Rejected	0.042	Difference
Price	Accepted	0.061	No difference
Satisfaction	Rejected	0.015	Difference

FINDINGS

- 54 respondents agree with consistency maintained by brands in their product quality.
- 48 respondents i.e., 29.62% strongly agree with repurchase intention are based on quality.
- 63 respondents are satisfied with prices and services with brand of personal care product.
- Majority of respondents were satisfied with commitment of brand for personal care product.
- 16 respondents very strongly agree about brand provides best quality products whereas 10 respondents very strongly disagree.
- Majority of respondents disagree on purchasing brand products if they increase price continuously.
- According to test, there is significant differences between quality and satisfaction across age and gender.
- There is positive correlation between Price of personal care product and Income level of consumers.

- It is shown that there is no significance difference between price and emotional attachment across gender and age.

CONCLUSION

The main objective is to study consumer brand emotional attachment towards personal care products plays a significant role in driving consumer purchasing behaviour. When consumers form an emotional connection with a brand, they are more likely to remain loyal to that brand, make repeat purchases, and recommend the products to others. Brands that effectively communicate their values, quality, and benefits can create a sense of trust and attachment with customers, leading to long-term brand loyalty. Therefore, understanding and nurturing emotional attachment towards personal care products can be a powerful tool for brands to establish a strong and lasting relationship with consumers.

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